

Draft Report

Microbial Protein for Human Consumption: Towards sustainable protein production

Product development and gut model analysis

Anthony W Watson^{1,2} , Matt Longshaw³ and Rebecca F Townsend^{1,2}

¹ School of Biomedical, Nutritional and Sports Sciences, Newcastle University, UK

² Human Nutrition and Exercise Nutrition Centre, Newcastle University, UK

³ Calysta UK Ltd

Anthony Watson - anthony.watson@newcastle.ac.uk

Rebecca Townsend - rebecca.townsend@newcastle.ac.uk

UK Plant-Based Food Retail Market, trends and potential for reformulation

Scope

The plant-based food retail market in the United Kingdom has experienced a period of contraction over the past three years, despite ongoing interest in sustainable protein sources and growing public awareness of the environmental implications of food choices. Data presented in the latest market insights report by the Good Food Institute Europe, drawing on Circana retail data and NIQ household panels, illustrates both the challenges and emerging opportunities facing the sector. While total retail sales across six major plant-based categories have declined in both value and volume terms, certain segments demonstrate resilience and potential for growth. A more nuanced interpretation suggests that market maturity, shifting consumer preferences, inflationary pressure, and retail channel dynamics have collectively influenced recent trends.

This section will give a narrative summary of the GFIE report and will focus on the UK with a focus on choosing foods most suitable food segments for fortification with the Calysta protein (full report can be found [here](#)). The trends in the UK are broadly consistent with patterns reported across many European countries, with some regional variations in market maturity and category-specific dynamics.

Total Market Performance and Trend Trajectory

In the 52 weeks ending January 2025, the total value of the UK plant-based food retail market stood at £898 million, representing a 4.5% decline from the previous year and a 3.4% fall compared to January 2023. In the same period, sales volume fell to 299 million kilograms – a reduction of 3.5% year-on-year and 10.6% over a two-year timeframe. While these headline figures indicate market contraction, it is important to note that the rate of decline in both unit sales and volume has moderated since 2023, suggesting a potential stabilisation of consumer demand.

A key factor influencing the observed decline in sales value in 2024–2025, despite near-level performance in 2023–2024, is the easing of food inflation which had previously masked underlying reductions in volume. The broader economic context, including high inflation and cost-of-living pressures, likely contributed to consumers re-evaluating discretionary purchases – a category into which many plant-based products still fall.

Category-Specific trends

Milk and Drinks

Plant-based milk and drink products continue to represent the most established and widely consumed segment in the UK plant-based food market. In the year to January 2025, this category accounted for £410.8 million in sales, equivalent to 46% of total plant-based retail value. Despite a decline of 2.9% in value and 3.0% in volume, this category remains comparatively stable and enjoys high household penetration.

Oat-based products lead this segment, comprising over 50% of total volume. The subcategory of barista-style milk exhibited notable growth, increasing from 39 to 48 million litres between 2023 and 2025. This suggests that innovations aligning with specific functional applications—such as coffee compatibility—are an effective lever for market differentiation and consumer retention.

Private-label products within this category are, on average, 39% cheaper than branded alternatives. Yet, branded items constitute the majority of sales volume, indicating that price is not the sole determinant of consumer choice in this category.

Meat Substitutes

The market for plant-based meat has shown sustained decline across all metrics. Sales value declined by 9.7% year-on-year and by over 15% over two years, to £333 million. NIQ household data corroborates these findings, showing that household penetration for plant-based meat fell from 38.7% in 2022 to 31.6% in 2024.

A number of interacting factors are likely at play: consumer concern around ultra-processed products, increased competitiveness of animal-based meat pricing, and product fatigue or dissatisfaction with current offerings. Notably, private-label products, while cheaper by 34%, constitute just 13% of category volume, further pointing to the significance of product quality and taste.

Frozen products now represent 57% of sales volume (up from 53%), reflecting a shift in consumer preference potentially driven by both cost and convenience. Within product types, red meat analogues dominate, with plant-based pork and beef accounting for 65% of the segment.

Yoghurt

Plant-based yoghurt is one of the few categories to show year-on-year growth. Sales volume rose by 6.5% to 19.7 million kilograms, while sales value increased by 6.3% to £92.1 million. Branded products dominate (93.6% of volume), and consumer preference continues to favour flavoured and low-fat

options. This growth may be indicative of the category's ability to respond to consumer expectations around taste, health, and versatility.

The price gap between plant-based and animal-based yoghurt has narrowed, with branded plant-based yoghurt now carrying only a 6% premium. This may partially explain the category's improved performance.

Cheese

Sales of plant-based cheese reached £43.3 million in the year to January 2025—a slight decline of 0.4% from the previous year but up 44.6% compared to January 2023. However, volume declined slightly (–2.6%) following a period of sharp growth. The average pack size appears to have decreased, likely due to rising popularity of snacking formats.

This category remains nascent in terms of overall market share but only 2.48% of branded cheese sales by volume are plant-based. Nonetheless, consumer acceptance of ready-to-use formats (slices and grated cheese) signals ongoing market adaptation. The average price of plant-based cheese remains 26% higher than animal-based equivalents.

Seafood

Although accounting for a small portion of overall plant-based sales, seafood has shown encouraging signs of growth. Sales value increased by 21.5% year-on-year to £6.3 million, while volume rose modestly to 529,000 kg. Chilled formats have gained significant traction, with their share of sales volume rising from 32% to 51% in a single year. Despite a widening price gap between branded and private-label products, consumers appear to favour premium branded options, possibly due to quality perceptions and product variety (e.g., unbreaded fillets).

Cream

Sales of plant-based chilled cream products have plateaued. Volume remained level at 2.0 million litres, and sales value declined marginally (–3.3%) to £12.2 million. The average price fell slightly in the most recent year, suggesting some price sensitivity in this segment. Notably, plant-based cream is cost-competitive with branded animal-based cream (1.6% premium), which may account for its relatively resilient performance. Double cream variants make up nearly half of all sales volume, and lentil-based products have grown in market share.

Private Label vs. Branded Products

Branded products account for the overwhelming majority of plant-based retail sales (approximately 90% by value). While private-label items are priced significantly lower across categories, their share of

the market has declined. In the year to January 2025, private-label sales volume fell by 8.9%, compared to a 2.3% drop for branded products.

This divergence suggests that attributes such as taste, product familiarity, and brand reputation continue to be decisive factors in purchase decisions, even in an inflationary environment.

Household Purchasing Behaviour

NIQ panel data highlights shifting patterns of consumer engagement with plant-based products. While plant-based meat experienced a decline in household penetration (from 38.7% to 31.6%), plant-based milk rose slightly (from 30.5% to 31.8%). Frequent purchasers of plant-based milk (12+ times annually) also increased modestly.

Across all categories with available comparative data, plant-based products remain more expensive than their animal-based counterparts, although price premiums have narrowed in select areas. Market share for plant-based products remains modest:

- Milk and drinks: 6.7% (by volume)
- Yoghurt: 4.3%
- Cheese: 2.48%
- Cream: 2.3%

Purchasers

A report by the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) (Stannard, 2018) which used a AHDB/YouGov tracker and data from Kantar world panel showed that a significant majority of the UK population (81%) identify as meat eaters. In contrast, only 7% describe themselves as vegetarians (consuming dairy and eggs but avoiding fish and meat), 4% as pescetarians (eating fish and dairy but not meat), and just 2% identify as vegans. While veganism tends to receive considerable media coverage, it remains a minority lifestyle choice, with only 0.2% of consumers fully giving up meat, fish, and poultry in the past year (Stannard, 2018). Notably, there is significant crossover between consumers of conventional animal products and those purchasing alternatives. For instance, half of all meat alternative sales come from self-identified meat eaters, indicating that many are experimenting or reducing rather than eliminating meat. Similarly, 45% of dairy alternative products are consumed alongside traditional dairy in the same eating occasion which highlights the blended habits of flexitarian consumers.

Conclusion

Overall market contraction has been driven by a combination of economic pressures, shifting consumer sentiment, and increased scrutiny of ultra-processed foods. Yet, a detailed category analysis reveals that growth opportunities remain particularly in plant-based milk and yoghurt and lesser so chilled plant based cream.

Target markets should not be solely focussed on those who do not consume conventional animal products but also consumers of traditional animal based products who wish to engage in a flexitarian type diet. For this reason, analogues which mimic plant-based meat sources and products where part substitution with an alternative protein source should be considered.

Reformulation potential of foods

The market analysis of plant based animal analogues informs us that plant-based milks and yoghurts have a stable consumer demand in a shrinking market. These are foods also which are also known to have amino acid profiles with potential to be improved using supplementary proteins.

Oat Based Milks and yoghurts

Oat based milks, yoghurts and cheeses continue to see volume of sales growth in the UK and offer good potential for reformulation using microbial protein. From a nutritional perspective, the protein content and quality of oat-based products is limited. Oats contain relatively low levels of protein, with typical concentrations in commercial oat-based milk ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 g per 100 ml (Chalupa-Krebdak, Long, & Bohrer, 2018; Jeske, Zannini, & Arendt, 2017), and in oat-based yoghurt from 1.5 to 3.5 g per 100 g. In addition to the quantity, the quality of oat protein is constrained by its amino acid profile with methionine being the limiting amino acid. (Yu et al., 2023).

Protein quality metrics such as the Protein Digestibility-Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS) indicate that the quality of oat protein is considerably lower than animal-derived proteins. The processing of oats impacts the PDCAAS of oats but the score ranges from 0.5 for flour and 0.6 for protein isolates (Sánchez-Velázquez et al., 2021) which is considerably below that of cow's milk, which scores 1.0. While some commercial formulations are fortified with higher-quality plant proteins such as pea or soy to improve their amino acid composition, unfortified oat-based milk and yoghurt should not be considered nutritionally equivalent to dairy in terms of protein quality.

Meat substitutes

Meat analogues have undergone significant research and development over the last decade. These are products made from non-animal sources but imitate traditional animal based products such as bacon, sausages beef burgers and mince. There are also popular alternatives for processed ready to eat foods such as chicken nuggets. Although the market share of these food have declined over the last 2 years, there is still considerable scope for redevelopment using microbial protein. This market is broad, and consumers are generally omnivorous but does encompass vegan and vegetarian consumer too. considerable research and development has been undertaken in the area of plant-based meat alternatives to complement EAAs from different plant sources to improve levels of limiting amino acids and improve the protein chemical score of the foods. However, the appearance of EAAs in human plasma after ingestion is still generally lower than that of their meat alternatives (Pham et al., 2022).

Product development

Foods selected based on their potential for reformulation and market share are Oat milk, oat yogurt, and vegetable meat analogues burgers and mince. Initial analysis was conducted to calculate the chemical score of reformulated foods which include 5 and 10% feed kind protein powder. Amino acid composition of foods were extracted from the literature and the amino acid composition of the feed kind powder was obtained through specification documents provided by Calysta UK. Reference essential amino acid profiles were taken from the 2013 Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations expert consultation report on dietary protein quality in human nutrition (FAO, 2013). Where EAA data were available for products, chemical scores were calculated using the equation $\frac{\text{mg of limiting EAA in test protein}}{\text{mg of same EAA in reference}} \times 100$. EAA content of foods were extracted from the literature. Data for oat milk was taken from (Stöckl et al., 2024) where mean data were presented for EAA content of four commercially available oat milks. Data for the plant based burger was taken from (Swing et al., 2021) where analysis was conducted on a readily commercially available plant based meat analogue burger (beyond burger) which can be used in analysis in the gut model in section 4. Oat yoghurt and vegetable mince AA compositions were taken from Domić et al., (2025). Results are displayed for the inclusion of 5% and 10% feed kind protein powder based on weight of the test food. Results can be found in table 1 for oat milk Table 2 for oat yoghurt Table 3 for beyond burgers and table 4 for vegetable mince.

Table 1 - Comparative analysis of essential amino acid profiles and nutritional quality among reference, oat milk, and blend protein samples

Amino acid	Reference 2013 (mg/g)	Oat milk (mg/g protein)	Blend 5% (mg/g protein)	Blend 10% (mg/g protein)	EAAS Oat milk	EAAS Blend (5%)	EAAS Blend (10%)
Histidine	16	16.61	18.89	19.11	103.8	118.07	119.45
Isoleucine	30	34.32	37.97	38.32	114.41	126.56	127.73
Leucine	61	61.88	64.06	64.27	101.44	105.02	105.36
Lysine	48	38.93	48.41	49.32	81.11	100.85	102.75
Methionine + Cysteine	23	33.05	29.16	28.79	143.71	126.79	125.16
Phenylalanine + Tyrosine	41	68.22	66.2	66	166.38	161.45	160.98
Threonine	25	26.77	36.7	37.66	107.08	146.82	150.65
Tryptophan	6.6	15.55	15.49	15.49	235.67	234.73	234.64
Valine	40	42.89	49.07	49.67	107.23	122.67	124.16
EAA score					81.11	100.85	102.75
Total EAA	290.6	338.22	365.95	368.63			
Protein (g / 100 g food)		0.74	4.20	7.66			
Energy (kcal / 100 g food)		160.14	169.93	179.72			
% Energy from Protein		1.84	9.89	17.06			

Reference value – FAO 2013. Oat milk data extracted from Stöckl et al., (2024). Orange colour depicts the limiting amino acid. mg/g = mg/gram of protein

Table 2 - Comparative analysis of essential amino acid profiles and nutritional quality among reference, oat yoghurt, and blend protein samples

Amino acid	Reference 2013 (mg/g)	Oat yoghurt (mg/g)	Blend 5% (mg/g)	Blend 10% (mg/g)	EAA Oat Yoghurt	EAAS Blend (5%)	EAAS Blend (10%)
Histidine	16.00	20.40	19.70	19.50	127.50	123.13	121.88
Isoleucine	30.00	49.00	44.10	42.90	163.33	147.00	143.00
Leucine	61.00	88.20	78.60	76.30	144.59	128.85	125.08
Lysine	48.00	70.60	56.80	54.60	147.08	118.33	113.75
Methionine + Cystine	23.00	43.30	35.30	33.90	188.26	153.48	147.39
Phenylalanine + Tyrosine	41.00	110.20	90.10	86.50	268.78	219.76	210.98
Threonine	25.00	42.90	39.70	38.80	171.60	158.80	155.20
Tryptophan	6.60	14.70	15.30	15.40	222.73	231.82	233.33
Valine	40.00	67.00	57.50	55.60	167.50	143.75	139.00
EAA score					127.50	118.33	113.75
Total EAA	290.60	506.30	437.10	423.50			
Protein (g / 100 g food)		3.30	6.80	10.30			
Energy (kcal / 100 g food)		145.00	156.10	167.20			
% Energy from Protein		9.10	17.40	24.70			

Reference value – FAO 2013. Oat milk data extracted from Domić et al, (2025). Orange colour depicts the limiting amino acid. mg/g = mg/gram of protein

Table 3 - Comparative analysis of essential amino acid profiles and nutritional quality among reference, oat beyond burger, and blend protein samples

Amino acid	Reference 2013 (mg/g)	Beyond (mg/g)	Blend 5% (mg/g)	Blend 10% (mg/g)	EAAS Beyond Burger	EAAS Blend (5%)	EAAS Blend (10%)
Histidine	16	21.2	20.91	20.68	132.5	130.7	129.26
Isoleucine	30	43.7	42.92	42.3	145.67	143.07	141
Leucine	61	76.5	74.63	73.14	125.41	122.35	119.9
Lysine	48	66.4	63.9	61.89	138.33	133.12	128.95
Methionine + Cystine	23	18.05	19.66	20.94	78.48	85.46	91.05
Phenylalanine + Tyrosine	41	34.6	39.45	43.33	84.39	96.22	105.69
Threonine	25	33.35	34.18	34.85	133.4	136.73	139.39
Tryptophan	6.6	8.35	9.46	10.35	126.52	143.32	156.76
Valine	40	45.6	46.33	46.92	114	115.83	117.3
EAA score					78.48	85.46	91.05
Total EAA	290.6	347.75	351.44	354.4			
Protein (g / 100 g food)		15.92	18.62	21.33			
Energy (kcal / 100 g food)		196	204	212			
% Energy from Protein		32.5	36.5	40.2			

Reference value – FAO 2013. Oat milk data extracted from Swing et al, (2021). Orange colour depicts the limiting amino acid. mg/g = mg/gram of protein

Table 4 - Comparative analysis of essential amino acid profiles and nutritional quality among reference, vegetable mince, and blend protein samples

Amino acid	Reference 2013 (mg/g)	veg mince (mg/g protein)	Blend 5% (mg/g protein)	Blend 10% (mg/g protein)	EAAS veg mince (%)	EAAS Blend (5%)	EAAS Blend (10%)
Histidine	16.00	26.00	24.80	23.90	162.50	155.00	149.38
Isoleucine	30.00	41.50	41.10	40.60	138.33	137.00	135.33
Leucine	61.00	76.60	74.50	72.70	125.57	122.13	119.18
Lysine	48.00	63.50	61.20	58.90	132.29	127.50	122.71
Methionine + Cystine	23.00	15.50	17.80	19.50	67.39	77.39	84.78
Phenylalanine + Tyrosine	41.00	79.00	76.70	74.80	192.68	187.07	182.44
Threonine	25.00	35.20	35.80	36.30	140.80	143.20	145.20
Tryptophan	6.60	8.60	9.80	10.80	130.30	148.48	163.64
Valine	40.00	46.80	47.40	47.90	117.00	118.50	119.75
EAA score					67.39	77.39	84.78
Total EAA	290.60	392.70	389.10	385.40			
Protein (g / 100 g food)		17.00	19.65	22.30			
Energy (kcal / 100 g food)		238.00	243.90	249.80			
% Energy from Protein		28.60	32.20	35.70			

Reference value – FAO 2013. Oat milk data extracted from Domic' et al, (2025). Orange colour depicts the limiting amino acid. mg/g = mg/gram of protein

Outcomes

The results from the desk-based analysis demonstrates that blending with a high-quality microbial protein source can substantially enhance both the EAA composition and overall protein content of plant based animal analogues. In the UK, food labelling regulations (Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006, retained in UK law) define products as a “source of protein” if at least 12% of their energy is derived from protein and as “high in protein” if 20% or more of the total energy comes from protein. These thresholds provide a useful benchmark for assessing the nutritional and commercial significance of the observed changes from our calculations.

In the case of oat milk, blending led to improvements in the protein quantity in foods and the quality. The total EAA content increased from 338.22 mg/g of protein in the control to 368.63 mg/g of protein in the 10% blend. The overall protein concentration increased substantially to 7.67g/ 100 g of food, the proportion of energy derived from protein also rose from 1.85% to 17.06%, bringing the 10% blend above to the threshold required to make a “source of protein” claim in the UK. This improvement is noteworthy given that standard oat milk formulations typically contain low levels of lysine and are not considered significant protein sources.

The oat yoghurt formulations showed a different trend. The starting product already had a strong amino acid profile, exceeding FAO reference values for several essential amino acids. The EAA levels reported by Domić et al. (2025) were typically higher than those reported in crude oat protein. This could be because the oat yoghurt product contains Potato Protein and other ingredients. Blending feed kind at 5% and 10% maintained balanced EAA levels in relation to the FAO reference, but considerably increasing protein content from 3.3 g/100 g in the control to 10.3 g/100 g in the 10% blend. The proportion of energy from protein increased from 9.1% to 17 and 24.7% respectively, meaning the 5% blend passed the source of protein threshold and the 10% blend would qualify as “high in protein” under UK nutrition claim criteria. Although some individual amino acid values declined slightly with the inclusion of feed kind, the overall amino acid balance and protein density remained excellent.

Similarly, the Beyond burger formulations improved amino acid balance and protein density with increasing feed kind blend percentage. The total EAA content reached 354.4 mg/g in the 10% blend, with lysine remaining the limiting amino acid. The increase in protein concentration (from 15.1 g/100 g to 21 g/100 g) and the corresponding rise in protein derived energy exceeds the 20% threshold for the “high in protein” classification.

Vegetable mince followed a comparable pattern. Although the total EAA content of the blended products was slightly lower than that of the unblended vegetable mince, improvements were observed in key amino acids such as methionine + cystine. The EAA score increased from 67.39 to 84.78. Protein content also rose from 17.0 g/100 g to 22.3 g/100 g. The proportion of energy derived from protein increased from 28.6% to for the 10% blend 35.7% with all formulations being above the 20% threshold for high in protein labelling.

Overall, the data indicate that blending with feed kind microbial protein can improve protein quality and amino acid quality across a range of popular market leading plant-based foods. The effect was most pronounced in low protein matrices such as oat milk, even high-protein bases such as vegetable mince and oat yoghurt benefited from blending in terms of improved amino acid profiles and energy contribution from protein. The above products make good candidates for gut model testing.

Product creation

Oat milk

Initial development of the oat milk (Oatly oat drink, Oatly UK Ltd) aimed to include 10% of microbial protein to the product. This quantity of protein powder was too high and resulted in the solution forming a thick, milkshake-like consistency. The aroma had a strong scent of the FeedKind powder,

masking the oat milk aroma completely. The serving size of Oatly milk is recommended to be 250ml by the manufacturer. It was decided to instead trial 5g and 10g of protein powder per serving of Oatly milk. As more protein powder was added to the Oatly milk, the milk appeared more brown in colour and slightly thicker in texture. The 5% protein powder will be taken forward for gut model analysis.

250ml Oatly milk
(standard)

250ml Oatly milk + 5g
Calysta protein powder

250ml Oatly milk + 10g
protein powder

Figure 2.

Oat Yoghurt

Products with 5g, 10g and 15g of protein per 150g of product were trailed. The trial yoghurt samples remained a similar texture to the standard, even with the powder added. The main change with the addition of Feedkind powder was a browning of colour where the pail yoghurt took on the brown colour of the powder.

150g Oatly Yoghurt
(standard)

150g Oatly Yoghurt +
10g Calysta protein
powder

150g Oatly Yoghurt +
15g Calysta protein
powder

Figure 3

Beyond burgers

A trial was run where the additional protein powder would make up 10% of a plant-based burger. Each burger weighed 113g. A standard burger was prepared and a trial burger was prepared where 10% of the burger consisted of the Calysta protein powder. Therefore, the trial burger weighed 100g with 13g Calysta powder added so that both burger weights were the same.

$$X = 0.10(113 + X)$$

$$X - 0.10X = 11.3$$

$$0.90X = 11.3$$

$X = 12.56g$ therefore 13g protein powder was added.

The burgers were grilled as per manufactures recommendations. The trial burger didn't hold shape compared to the original. The trial turned crumbly and powdery in texture once cooked. It also appeared dryer compared to the original. The original was more moist during cooking.

Raw:

Original Beyond Burger (left) and trial Beyond Burger with 13g Calysta protein (right)

Cooked:

Original Beyond Burger (left) and trial Beyond Burger with 13g Calysta protein (right)

Figure 4

This Isn't Beef Mince

A trial similar to the Beyond Burgers was conducted using plant-based mince. The mince weighed 246.5g over all and was split into 2 portions of 123.3g.

One of the portions didn't contain protein powder (original) and the other portion contained 10% Calysta protein powder (trial). The amount of protein powder that needed to be added to the trial sample was then calculated:

$$10\%: 0.1 \times 123.3g = 12.33g \text{ protein powder}$$

$$123.3g - 12.33g = 110.27g \text{ mince weight}$$

The two mince samples were then cooked in a pan with 1 tbsp vegetable oil at medium heat for 8 minutes. The trial sample was much powdery compared to the original when raw. After cooking, the trial mince appeared a darker brown colour compared to the original. The original appeared redder in colour and more moist.

Figure 5

Beef burgers

Beef burgers were chosen as the control in the gut model. An original sample and a test sample were produced, with the test sample containing 10% feedkind protein by weight.

One beef burger was weighed as **169.4g** and did not have any protein powder added (original).

Another burger weighing **169.4g** was adjusted in weight to add 10% protein powder (trial):

10%: $0.1 \times 169.4\text{g} = 16.94\text{g}$ protein powder

$169.4\text{g} - 16.94\text{g} = 152.46\text{g}$ burger weight

The trial burger was therefore reduced to **152.46g** in weight and **16.94g** protein powder was added, so that both burgers weighed **169.4g**.

The two burgers were then baked in a domestic oven at 200C for 20 minutes and flipped halfway through.

The original burger appeared redder in colour and the trial burger was browner when raw. The trial burger was powdery in texture when raw compared to the original. When cooking, the original burger remained intact however the trial burger didn't maintain its shape or consistency and released more juice than the original. When cooked, parts of the trial burger were dry on the outside but internal parts remained moist. The original was moist throughout.

Raw:

Original Beef Burger (left) and trial burger with 10% Calysta protein powder (right)

Cooked:

Original Beef Burger (left) and trial burger with 10% Calysta protein powder (right)

Figure 6

Table 6. Final protein content of prepared products

Food	Protein (g) / 100g product	Feedkind (g) /100g product	Protein from microbial powder per 100g	Total protein per 100g	Total protein per serving
Oat milk	1.10	0.00	0.00	1.10	2.75
Oat milk + 5g microbial protein per 250ml serving	1.1	2.4	1.68	2.78	6.95
Oatgurt yoghurt	3.30	0.00	0.00	3.30	4.95
Oatgurt + 10g microbial protein per 150g serving	3.30	6.6	4.73	8.3	12.45
Beef burger cooked	23.60	0.00	0.00	23.60	
Beef burger cooked + 10% microbial protein by weight	21.24	10.00	7.10	28.34	
Veg mince cooked	17.20	0.00	0.00	17.20	
Veg mince cooked + 10% microbial protein by weight	15.48	10.00	7.10	22.58	
Beyond burger cooked	14.40	0.00	0.00	14.40	
Beyond burger cooked + 10% microbial protein by weight	12.96	10.00	7.10	20.06	

Gut model analysis

An in vitro simulation of gastrointestinal digestion cumulative of the mouth, stomach and small intestine was carried out in a fed state, adapted from the published methods of (Houghton et al., 2014). This model was operated in a miniaturised format, with volumes reduced 1/40 from the full-scale model gut system. Food samples were added to the model such that the starting total protein content was 30mg per sample. Samples were taken from the model at T240 minutes, and the T240 endpoint samples were hydrolysed and analysed to determine amino acid content.

Samples.

Food samples were digested in the mini model gut in triplicate. Food samples were added to the model to give a starting protein content of 30mg. DI water was added to equalise the volumes of all the samples.

Procedure:

The experiment was carried out in 50ml Falcon tubes, and in a 37°C oscillating incubator. To each Falcon tube:

1. T0: Add 250µl saliva, 250µl DI water
 - a. Add the food samples and DI water to equalise volumes
 - b. Add 1.25ml gastric juice
2. T15: Add 375µl gastric juice
3. T30: Add 375µl gastric juice
4. T60: Add 375µl gastric juice
5. T90: Add 375µl gastric juice
6. T120: Add 500µl bile and 1.125ml pancreatic juice
7. T135: Add 375µl pancreatic juice
8. T150: Add 375µl pancreatic juice
9. T180: Add 375µl pancreatic juice
10. T210: Add 375µl pancreatic juice
11. T240: Take T240 sample (500µl)

The T240 samples were mixed with 500µl trichloroacetic acid (TCA), these samples and the final model gut solution were stored at -20°C for future analysis. The remaining model gut solution was frozen without precipitation.

BCA assay

The ThermoFisher Scientific Pierce BCA protein assay kit (Part number: 23227) was used according to the manufacturer's SOP to quantify total protein in foods produced and endpoint mini model gut samples.

Food samples were used as provided or after processing by placing 0.5g material in a pestle and mortar, carefully grinding the material to a paste, then adding 5ml PBS to rinse the contents into a bijoux tube

(processed). Samples were then diluted 1:10 or 1:20 in PBS to ensure the protein concentration fell within the standard curve.

1. Oat milk- as provided, diluted 1:10
2. Oat milk + protein- as provided, diluted 1:20
3. Oatgurt yoghurt- as provided, diluted 1:20
4. Oatgurt milk + protein- as provided, diluted 1:20
5. Beef burger cooked- processed, diluted 1:10
6. Beef burger cooked + protein- processed, diluted 1:10
7. Veg mince cooked- processed, diluted 1:10
8. Veg mince cooked + protein- processed, diluted 1:10
9. Beyond burger cooked- processed, diluted 1:10
10. Beyond burger cooked + protein- processed, diluted 1:10

Model gut samples: these were used undiluted

1. Model gut blank
2. Oat milk
3. Oat milk + protein
4. Oatgurt yoghurt
5. Oatgurt milk + protein
6. Beef burger cooked
7. Beef burger cooked + protein
8. Veg mince cooked
9. Veg mince cooked + protein
10. Beyond burger cooked
11. Beyond burger cooked + protein

Protein hydrolysis

Acid hydrolysis exposes samples to HCl vapour, and yields all amino acids with the exception of tryptophan, cystine and methionine which are unstable under these conditions. Hydrolysed samples were then derivatised using the Agilent online FMOC OPA derivatisation kit (part number 5190-9426) on the HPLC following the manufacturer's SOP.

The N1 replicate samples of oat milk, oat milk + protein, oatgurt, oatgurt + protein, veg mince, and veg mince + protein samples were sent for external analysis to quantify cysteic acid and tryptophan.

Procedure

Samples were first transferred into Kimble reaction tubes, which were then placed within a reaction vessel and dried under vacuum to remove residual moisture. Once dried, 200 μ L of a 1% phenol solution in 6 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) was added to the reaction vessel. To ensure an anaerobic and moisture-free environment, the vessel was purged through four vacuum/nitrogen cycles before being hermetically sealed.

The sealed reaction vial was then incubated in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours to facilitate hydrolysis. Following incubation, 10 µL of a 2:2:1 ethanol:water:triethylamine solution was added to each reaction tube to neutralize residual acid. The samples were subsequently re-dried under vacuum in preparation for further analytical processing.

Protein quality calculations

1. Protein Digestibility Corrected Amino Acid Scores we calculated following the methods specified in the Dietary protein quality evaluation in human nutrition FOA expert consultation report (2013). This uses the amino acid content of a protein source along with a digestibility ratio to determine the limiting amino acid and so calculate the PDCAAS. The following calculation was used $(EAAS \times \frac{digestibility (\%)}{100})$ where EAAS was calculated using $\frac{mg \text{ of limiting EAA in test protein}}{mg \text{ of same EAA in reference}} \times 100$.

Results

Digestibility

Figure 7 – Gut model digestibility of total protein in foods. Baseline data derived from calculated values. Post data derived from BCA values

Amino acid content of foods

Table 7 Amino acid content of foods

Amino acid	Ref 2013 (mg/g)	oat milk (mg/g)	oat milk + protein (mg/g)	Oatgurt (mg/g)	Oatgurt + protein (mg/g)	Beef burger (mg/g)	Beef burger + protein (mg/g)	Veg mince (mg/g)	Veg mince + protein (mg/g)	Beyond burger (mg/g)	Beyond burger + protein (mg/g)
Histidine	16	11.01	14.73	16.34	24.81	26.39	26.49	22.76	19.86	18.02	16.34
Isoleucine	30	28.54	31.36	32.35	40.92	46.80	41.22	44.13	42.29	45.91	36.90
Leucine	61	60.73	79.59	73.22	80.76	68.07	74.68	73.20	73.98	75.80	71.83
Lysine	48	29.55	68.31	67.20	67.88	69.46	56.37	60.96	58.05	64.99	60.10
Met + Cys	23	35.41	61.18	82.54	93.16	22.66	21.23	48.47	43.37	11.84	13.71
Phen + Tyre	41	40.67	58.12	55.06	66.17	64.54	56.61	67.59	68.69	79.26	61.38
Threonine	25	31.13	41.11	53.63	63.27	36.72	47.81	37.05	43.82	40.80	42.44
Tryptophan	7	11.31	31.90	21.42	47.17			37.06	27.07		
Valine	40	42.33	55.07	51.37	57.17	52.70	47.90	45.35	47.91	48.68	47.80

Reference value – FAO 2013. Orange colour depicts the limiting amino acid. Gray = outcome not measured

Table 8 Essential amino acid score of foods

Amino Acid	oat milk	oat milk + protein	Oatgurt	Oatgurt + protein	Beef burger	Beef burger + protein	Veg mince	Veg mince + protein	Beyond burger	Beyond burger + protein
Histidine	68.84	92.06	102.15	155.05	164.92	165.58	142.27	124.12	112.63	102.15
Isoleucine	95.13	104.53	107.85	136.39	156.01	137.40	147.10	140.95	153.04	122.99
Leucine	99.57	130.48	120.04	132.39	111.58	122.43	119.99	121.28	124.26	117.76
Lysine	61.56	142.30	140.00	141.41	144.71	117.43	126.99	120.94	135.39	125.20
Met + Cys	153.98	266.01	358.87	405.03	98.53	92.30	210.75	188.55	51.46	59.60
Phen+ Tyr	99.21	141.75	134.30	161.39	157.42	138.08	164.85	167.53	193.33	149.71
Threonine	124.54	164.44	214.53	253.09	146.90	191.24	148.19	175.26	163.21	169.75
Tryptophan	171.37	483.33	324.60	714.71			561.52	410.20		
Valine	105.83	137.68	128.43	142.92	131.74	119.74	113.39	119.76	121.70	119.51
EAAS	61.56	92.06	102.15	132.39	98.53	92.30	113.39	119.76	51.46	59.60

Reference value – FAO 2013. Orange colour depicts the limiting amino acid. Gray = outcome not analysed

PDCASS

Table 9 Protein digestibility corrected amino acid scores

Food	Limiting AA	EAAS (%)	Digestibility (%)	PDCAAS
oat milk	Lysine	61.56	86.91	0.535
oat milk + protein	Histidine	92.06	92.88	0.855
Oatgurt	Histidine	102.15	88.67	0.887
Oatgurt + protein	Leucine	132.39	91.81	0.918
Beef burger	Met+Cys	98.53	95.17	0.938
Beef burger + protein	Met+Cys	92.30	95.46	0.881
Veg mince	Valine	113.39	93.31	0.933
Veg mince + protein	Valine	119.76	94.44	0.944
Beyond burger	Met+Cys	51.46	92.92	0.478
Beyond burger + protein	Met+Cys	59.60	94.43	0.563

Trp was not quantified for Beyond burger or beef burger

Overall outcomes

The amino acid analysis (table 7) revealed substantial variability in protein quality across the foods tested. As expected, animal-derived protein (beef burger) has a balanced essential amino acid (EAA) profile and high digestibility, aligning with previously reported data for animal-source proteins

(FAO/WHO, 2013). However, fortification with additional protein markedly improved the amino acid composition of all plant-based and mixed products, particularly those derived from oats. Oat-based matrices are typically limited by lysine deficiency, a characteristic of cereal proteins, but the inclusion of the microbial protein powder increased lysine content by more than twofold in oat milk and Oatgurt. This improvement raised the Essential Amino Acid Scores above 100%, meeting FAO/WHO amino acid requirements for adults.

Protein digestibility in the gut model was high across all samples, ranging from 86.9% to 95.5%. The slight advantage observed in animal-based products is consistent with established data showing superior digestibility of animal proteins. Nevertheless, the digestibility of plant-based products containing microbial protein was comparably high. Notably, protein addition had a modest but consistent positive impact on digestibility across the plant-based matrices. This outcome is coupled with increased total protein levels.

Protein fortification generally improved both the amino acid balance and overall protein quality of the plant-based foods, with modest or neutral effects observed in animal-based products.

Oat-based products showed the largest improvements following protein addition. In oat milk, the limiting amino acid shifted from lysine to histidine, and the EAAS increased from 61.56% to 92.06%, with digestibility rising from 86.9% to 92.9%, resulting in a PDCAAS increase from 0.535 to 0.855. Similarly, Oatgurt improved from an EAAS of 102.15% to 132.39% and a PDCAAS of 0.887 to 0.918.

Plant-based meat analogues also benefitted from the inclusion of microbial protein. Veg mince + protein achieved one of the highest PDCAAS values (0.944) compared to the unfortified sample (0.933), reflecting an already high baseline protein quality that was further optimized by supplementation. Beyond Burger showed a modest improvement from 0.478 to 0.563, driven by higher methionine + cysteine content and slightly better digestibility, although these sulfur amino acids remained limiting.

Animal-based products displayed little or no improvement upon fortification. Beef burger and Beef burger + protein had comparable digestibility (95.17% vs. 95.46%) and similar PDCAAS values (0.938 vs. 0.881), indicating that additional protein did not significantly enhance the amino acid profile and may have slightly diluted the balanced amino acid composition of the original product.

Colonic model

An in vitro model of the microbial environment of the human colon was generated using a faecal sample to develop a representative population of the transverse colon. The model includes dynamic modelling of microbial populations, fermentation processes, and metabolite production in the colon.

Samples:

Three beakers of each sample were run through the model, dialysed, then pooled and mixed 50:50 with media to feed the colonic model.

- Beyond burger (cooked)- 100g
- Beyond burger + 10% protein microbial protein (cooked)- 100g

Procedure:

A water bath was preheated to 37°C, and the model gut beakers were placed within the bath to maintain physiological temperature throughout the procedure. Each digestion experiment was performed under continuous stirring to ensure homogeneity. To begin, 10 mL of simulated saliva and 10 mL of deionised (DI) water were added to each model gut vessel, after which the stirrers were activated. The test sample was then introduced into the vessel.

To initiate gastric digestion, 50 mL of simulated gastric juice was added to the vessel, marking the start of the time course (T₀). Immediately following this addition, the continuous delivery of gastric juice was commenced at a rate of 0.5 mL/min using a peristaltic pump to mimic physiological gastric secretion.

After 120 minutes of gastric digestion (T₁₂₀), the intestinal phase was initiated by adding 25 mL of bile and 45 mL of pancreatic juice to the vessel. At this stage, the peristaltic pump feed was switched from gastric juice to pancreatic juice to simulate intestinal secretion. The digestion was then continued until T₂₄₀ minutes, representing the completion of the small intestinal phase.

At the end of digestion (T₂₄₀), samples were collected and subjected to dialysis using 12–14 kDa molecular weight cut-off dialysis tubing. The samples were dialysed against DI water for six buffer changes over two days at 4°C to remove low-molecular-weight components. Following dialysis, the digested samples were frozen at –20°C until further analysis.

Colonic fermentation model

The in vitro colonic model is based on the three-stage fermentation model established by Macfarlane et al (1998). In this experiment, the model was operated such that it was reflective of conditions in the transverse colon.

The dialysed endpoint digested solution from the full-scale model gut was used to feed the colonic model.

Collection and preparation of donor samples

A faecal sample was collected from one donor using the FeCol collection kit. Approximately 2 g of sample was obtained using the provided spoon and placed into a 25 ml universal tube. The sample was then mixed thoroughly with 10 ml of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and 5 ml of this suspension was used to inoculate each of the two colon model vessels. The colon model was subsequently allowed to equilibrate for two days prior to the addition of the test samples. The faecal donor was a 27-year-old female.

The assembly and sterilisation of the colonic model followed a series of steps to ensure appropriate preparation and maintenance of an anaerobic environment. The Culture Medium for Gut Microbes (CMGM) was prepared according to the method described by Macfarlane et al. (1998). Each vessel was filled with 200 ml of PBS, after which the autoclavable pH probe was inserted. The vessels were connected to one another, and the feed line and feed bottle were attached to the system. The entire model, including the media, was sterilised by autoclaving and allowed to cool before further use.

Once cooled, each vessel and its corresponding feed bottle were positioned on a stirrer plate to maintain homogeneity during fermentation. The pH probe was connected to the controller, and acid and base lines were attached to bottles containing 1 M NaOH and 1 M HCl, respectively. The pH controllers were programmed to automatically titrate the contents of each vessel within the range of pH 6.1–6.3. The feed bottle was then connected, and CMGM was pumped through the system to fill each vessel. The pump speed was adjusted to 0.3 rpm, corresponding to a media delivery rate of 150 ml per day.

To establish anaerobic conditions, the gas line was attached, and the system was sparged with nitrogen gas. Finally, the vessels were inoculated with the prepared faecal sample and left to ferment continuously for two days, allowing the microbial population to stabilise before experimental testing commenced.

Running the experiment

After two days of continuous culture, the experiment was started. 300ml of each sample was mixed 1:1 with culture medium for gut microbes (CMGM) to give a 600ml solution that was used to feed the colonic model over the 4 days of the experiment. A 5ml sample was taken at T0, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hours.

Sample preparation

At each timepoint a 5ml sample was taken. 1ml of each sample was aliquoted into a microcentrifuge tube and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The entire supernatant was taken and placed into a fresh microcentrifuge tube. The pellet and the remaining 3.5 mL sample were stored at -20°C, and the supernatant was stored at -80°C.

For short chain fatty acid quantification, the supernatant was sent away for external analysis via GC-MS.

For 16s rRNA sequencing of the microbiome, the pellets were defrosted and DNA was extracted using the Qiagen QIAamp PowerFecal Pro DNA kit and sent to Eurofins for sequencing. The microbiome was assessed by 16s RNA sequencing of the V3-V4 region (primers- fwd: TACGGGAGGCAGCAG and rev: CCAGGGTATCTAATCC, using an ILLUMINA MiSeq system.

The following analyses were performed:

- Beta diversity analysis
- Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA)
- Alpha diversity analysis

Figure 8 - colonic model

Results

Short Chain Fatty Acids

The short chain fatty acid (SCFA) data were returned in mM concentrations for the T0 and T96 hour time points for each sample (Figure 9). Acetic acid concentrations decreased from 37.4mM to 30.8mM in the beyond burger sample, and from 35.9mM to 33.4mM in the burger & protein sample over 96 hours. Propionic acid concentrations decreased from 25.8mM to 14.3mM in the beyond burger sample and increased from 23.9mM to 24.9mM in the burger & protein sample over 96 hours. Butyric acid concentrations decreased from 9.1mM to 1.8mM in the beyond burger sample and from 24.0 to 20.5mM in the burger & protein sample over 96 hours. Isobutyrate and isovalerate were only present in the T96 burger & protein sample at 1.3mM and 1.4mM respectively.

Overall, SCFA production decreased more markedly in the Beyond Burger samples, suggesting lower fermentative activity or altered microbial metabolism compared to the Burger & Protein samples.

Figure 9- Short Chain Fatty Acid content of the three-stage fermentation model samples. Samples were taken from each of the two vessels at T0 and T96 hours after addition of the digested burger samples. SCFA were quantified by GCMS.

Microbiome Analysis

Genus-level Relative Abundance

Sequencing provided data for Operational Taxonomic Units (OTU) which are summarised at the Genus level below. Any OTUs with an average abundance level of less than 0.5% across all samples are removed, and the remaining OTUs are processed for comparative statistical analysis. Figure 4 illustrates the relative abundance of various genera within the microbial community.

The x-axis showcases distinct samples, while the y-axis represents the relative abundance of each genus, with bar heights indicating the proportion of the total community each genus occupies. The colours of the bars correspond to different genera, facilitating easy visualization of the community composition.

This snapshot of the microbial community at the genus level allows for the identification of dominant genera, potential imbalances, and shifts in community composition. By comparing the relative abundance of genera across samples, one can gain valuable insights into the dynamics of the microbial community and its responses to varying conditions.

As Figure 10 shows, each sample contained a distinct microbial population, and addition of the food samples affected the populations differently. In the Beyond burger T0 sample, the prevalent genera are *Bifidobacterium* (11.22%) and *Collinsella* (27.30%), and at T96 these are *Prevotella* (56.38%) and *Desulfovibrio* (17.03%). In the Burger & protein sample, *Prevotella* (49.44%) and *Faecalibacterium* (26.2%) dominate at T0 and *Bacteroides* (28.43%) and *Barnesiella* (10.36%) are most prevalent at T96.

Figure 10- Visualisation of the relative abundance of each genus in samples taken from the colonic model, arranged by sample and timepoint. The colonic model was run for 48 hours after inoculation, prior to addition of the beyond burger (B) and beyond burger & protein (BP) digested samples at T0. The model was then operated for 96 hours with a final sample taken at T96 hours. Samples were analysed by 16s rRNA sequencing of the V3-V4 region and aligned with known operational taxonomic

units (OTUs). The x-axis shows sample type and time point. The y-axis shows the proportion of each OTU classified. Data are n=1.

Beta Diversity Analysis

Beta diversity analysis using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity is a method to quantify differences in the overall taxonomic composition between two sample groups. The Bray-Curtis dissimilarity is a metric that examines the abundances of microbes shared between two sample groups and the number of microbes found in each. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates identical communities and 1 indicates completely different communities.

The calculation of Bray-Curtis dissimilarity takes into account the abundance of shared microbes in two sample groups, and it is commonly used in microbiome studies to assess differences between groups or treatments.

As Figure 11 shows, the T0 samples for each food sample are the most similar, and 96 hours after addition of the food samples, the composition of each bacterial community has changed, with the greatest change occurring between the Beyond burger T0 and T96 samples.

Figure 11- Heatmap showing the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity of samples taken from the in vitro colonic model. Hierarchical relationships between the samples are presented by the dendrograms above and to the side of the heat map. Individual samples and timepoints (Beyond burger, B; Beyond burger & protein, BP; T0, T96) are presented here separately. A dissimilarity of 1 (red colour) indicates communities are different, and a dissimilarity of 0 (blue colour) indicates communities are similar.

Principle coordinates Analysis

Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) is a valuable method for visualizing and understanding the relationships and clusters within complex datasets based on their dissimilarity. In the plot, each point represents a sample, and the distances between points reflect the dissimilarity between microbial communities (beta diversity). A non-parametric test, PERMANOVA (permutation-based Analysis of Variance) is performed to test for significance between the groups or conditions using ranked dissimilarities (beta diversity) generated from OTU composition tables.

The PCoA analysis of the samples (Figure 12) encapsulates 79.72% of the sample dissimilarity within two axes. This is fractionally below the 80% threshold that is typically considered successful for this analysis, this is likely due to the small number of test samples. Some clustering of the T0 samples can be seen, indicating that these samples had the most similar composition.

Figure 12- Principle Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) of samples taken from the in vitro colonic model. The PCoA plot visualises the Bray-Curtis dissimilarities of the samples. The x and y axes show the first and second principal coordinates that contain the most significant variance of the data. Each sample from each time point and food sample is plotted separately as indicated in the key. A PERMANOVA statistical test was performed to determine the difference between the samples, but no significant difference was found.

Alpha Diversity

Alpha diversity indices offer a powerful tool for analysing the complexity and diversity of microbiome samples. The analysis employed the Shannon index, a widely used metric for measuring alpha diversity, to quantify the richness and evenness of microbial communities across multiple samples.

The Shannon index considers both the number of unique species present (richness) and the relative abundance of each species (evenness), providing a comprehensive measure of community diversity. A high Shannon index indicates that a sample contains a richer and more even bacterial population, whereas a lower value indicates that a sample contains a population that is dominated by a few genera or fewer genera are represented.

As Table 2 shows, the Shannon diversity decreased over 96 hours for the Beyond burger sample, and increased over the same time course for the Burger & protein sample.

Table 9- Alpha diversity (Shannon index) of samples taken from the in vitro colonic model. This ranges from 0 (indicating only 1 genus was found) to a theoretical upper limit of 3.56 for this experiment.

Sample	Shannon Index
B_T0	2.48
B_T96	1.49
BP_T0	1.64
BP_T96	2.48